

#048 Phase field fracture modelling for 3D printed materials: a preliminary study

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3D printing

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Abstract

Abstract In recent years, Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM) has captured more and more interest among both industrial and academic players due to the incredible opportunities that this technology offers. In this field, one particular branch seems to be promising for the possibilities offered from the design point of view: the continuous carbon fibre deposition. The possibility of depositing continuous Carbon Fibre (CF) along with common polymeric material allows the designer to give particular attention to regions of the component which could be subjected to higher stresses for whichever reason (notches, discontinuities, joints). The reinforcement of such areas with CF allows a better resistance to catastrophic phenomena like fracture which could lead to the failure of the component. Therefore, this deposition technique is of particular interest and object of study in this work. In the first part, a problem studied experimentally by Akasheh et al. [1] is analyzed numerically by means of the Phase Field fracture modelling, demonstrating the optimal capabilities of this approach to capture not only the experimental crack path but also the Stress-Strain response of the specimens tested. Validation of the material parameters is of particular importance especially for novel materials like the ones used in the experiments performed by the authors. Once both the capabilities of Phase Field and the material properties have been verified by means of the numerical simulations described above, these are now exploited to study a well know problem in the field of mechanics and aeronautics: structural joints. The aim is to use Phase Field as a tool able to predict failure load and failure mode of a component subjected to operating loading conditions, for instance. This could allow the designer to exploit the capabilities of continuous carbon fibre deposition to generate fracture resistance components, by means of accurate reinforcement of the most critical regions, where failure is most likely to occur. The Open Hole Tension test is simulated numerically by means of the same tools described above, taking into consideration different geometries for the reinforcement around the hole. The specimens with different reinforcements show different mechanical responses and crack patterns, thus highlighting the influence of the continuous carbon fibre reinforcement on the fracture scenario.

[1] Akasheh, F. and H. Aglan (2019). Fracture toughness enhancement of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites utilizing additive manufacturing fabrication. *Journal of Elastomers and Plastics* 51 (7-8), 698–711.